

PROVIDING ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING TO PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE FAMILY

Durmanova G.D.

Surkhandarya Regional Center for Pedagogical Skills senior teacher of the department of
"Pedagogy, psychology and education technologies"

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Abstract. *The purpose of this article is to teach preschool children to save and explore natural resources and protect nature.*

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The purpose of environmental education and upbringing in the family is to encourage a person to consciously use nature throughout his life, from the moment he steps into nature, to educate the younger generations of our people in terms of psychology, morality and ethics, to respect and care for nature, to increase its natural resources, to organize gardens and flower beds, and to instill good qualities in their hearts. In the process of ecological education, young people are taught to conserve natural resources and protect nature.

The main goal of ecological education is to increase the ecological literacy of society, to protect nature, keep it clean, and to care for nature by encouraging environmentally conscious, educated people to love animals, birds, and plants.

How a person develops into a person depends to a large extent on upbringing in the family, on the responsibility of parents, how well they know the general laws of child upbringing and how much they follow them in life. Parents are responsible for the education of their children before the society. Parents are the main educators of their children. That is why they should raise their children to be noble, knowledgeable, ecologically cultured people in the spirit of the best customs and family traditions of their people.

In order to develop ecological spirituality among young people, it is necessary to explain to them the ecological spiritual heritage of their people, which has been formed since ancient times. That's how the generations continue the traditions, taking the example from their ancestors. If we look at the ecological and spiritual heritage of our people, we can be sure that our grandparents had a high ecological culture in the past.

For example, many developed countries are trying to preserve their natural resources as much as possible. After all, as Uzbek people say, "even a mountain cannot withstand a person who lies down and eats". However, we, the children of such a wise people, do not follow the teachings of our ancestors and use elements such as electricity, gas, and water without saving, as if they were inexhaustible.

The concept of "waste" has been very widespread among our people since ancient times. The aimless use of natural elements, namely water, soil, and plants, was considered waste. Today, most young people do not even know what waste is. The concept of waste applied equally to everyone, regardless of whether people were rich or poor. Not wasting money, not doing useless things, not wasting anything, and being thrifty is not a sign of stinginess, as some people think, but a sign of high ecological spirituality. The quality of thrift was instilled in the younger generation from childhood, and this spirituality was preserved until the end of their lives. If it was

noticed that someone's spirituality was beginning to deteriorate, the public would remind them in a beautiful way how to behave.

Uzbeks have long used any raw material rationally, even if it is pure soil lying underfoot. The peoples of Central Asia, including Uzbek people, have long had an ecological cultural heritage. Our most reliable, ancient manuscript, "Avesto," is considered the invaluable property of our people. This rare book is the spiritual and historical heritage of our ancestors who lived on this land thirty centuries ago, which we have left to our descendants. "Avesto" is also a historical document testifying to the fact that at that time, this ancient land had a great state, high spirituality and culture. "Avesto" is a philosophy that harmonizes the relationships between nature, society and man through spiritual and moral criteria, and encourages a person to study the world around him. "Avesto" contains valuable information about unique medicinal herbs. In addition, recommendations are given on the protection and preservation of housing, the environment, and nature. The Avesto talks about keeping the earth, water, rooms, human body parts, and clothes clean. People who polluted the environment, streets, bushes, meadows and land were punished. It also ordered that garbage and contaminated areas be buried with stones, soil, and sand in order to maintain environmental cleanliness and prevent diseases. The work also shows ways to eliminate disease-spreading insects, as well as properly care for pets.

Among the scientists who lived and worked in Central Asia in the Middle Ages, Muhammad Musa al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Rayhan al-Biruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Al-Farghani and others made a great contribution to the development of natural science. At a time when the science of ecology had not yet emerged, they expressed valuable ideas about nature and its balance, the flora and fauna, and respect for nature. The great scholar Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi (783–850) wrote in one of his treatises: "Know that when the eyes of a river shed tears, sorrow and trouble have befallen it. People, do not withhold your love from the river!". What did Muhammad Musa al-Khwarizmi mean by the "teary eyes" of a river? Perhaps he meant the excessive waste of river water? However, our great grandfather, first of all, meant that people with a river "understand each other" and love each other. In 847, Muhammad al-Khwarizmi wrote his work "Kitab surat al-arz". It contains information about the world's oceans, land continents, poles, equators, deserts, mountains, rivers and seas, lakes and forests, their flora and fauna, as well as the main wealth of the earth and other natural resources. This treatise summarizes mathematics, geology, astronomy, ethnography, medicine, as well as the natural skills and historical and legal knowledge of the peoples of the world.

Abu Nasr Al-Farabi. The scientific and philosophical heritage of Abu Nasr Al-Farabi (873–950 AD), one of the largest and most famous representatives of the socio-philosophical thoughts of the peoples of Central Asia, is extremely rich. His works have not yet been fully identified. The list of the German scientist M.K. Brockelmann lists 180 works by Al-Farabi in various fields. Al-Farabi was engaged in various branches of natural science, and his works "Kitab al-hajm va al-miqdar", "Kitab al-mabodi al-insonia" ("Book on the Origin of Humanity"), "Kitab al-a'za al-hayvan" ("Book on the Parts of Animals") serve as evidence of this. In his works on natural science, such as "The Structure of Human Organs" and "On the Organs of Animals and Their Functions," he also discussed the structure, properties, and functions of certain organs in humans and animals. When discussing the structure and functions of human organs, he explained that changes, that is, diseases, are primarily caused by nutritional disorders. Al-Farabi distinguished between natural and artificial things created by human hands. He also emphasized that natural

things are created by nature and that the human factor has a great influence on them, and he thoroughly evaluated natural and artificial selection and other influences on nature.

Abu Rayhan Beruni (973–1048 AD) tried to explain the phenomena of the universe by the laws of development, the interaction of objects and phenomena. The scientist explained some phenomena on Earth by the influence of the sun. According to Beruni, the necessary opportunities for the existence of the plant and animal world on Earth are limited. However, plants and animals always strive to multiply and fight for this purpose. Beruni's following thoughts as a naturalist have not lost their relevance to this day: "The world is filled with crops and offspring. Although the world is limited, as the days pass, reproduction as a result of these two growths is not limited. If there are no conditions for the growth of one species of plants or animals and they stop growing, this situation does not happen with others. They do not appear suddenly and disappear suddenly. If the earth were completely covered by the same tree or the same animal, there would be no room for the animal to reproduce or for the tree to grow. For this reason, farmers would weed the crops and uproot the unnecessary ones. In the works of Beruni, one can find information about the biological characteristics of plants and animals, their distribution and importance in the economy. Beruni's scientific views were mainly reflected in the works "Saydana", "Mineralogy", "Monuments of Ancient Generations". In them, the relationship of various tropical plants and animals of Iran with the external environment, their behavior with the change of seasons, is explained with examples. Beruni believes that the change in the earth's surface should be associated with the change in the flora and fauna, and the different life of living organisms with the history of the earth. You can dig up sand and find a shell among it. The reason for this is that these sands were once the bottom of the ocean, the scientist claims. In his work "Saydana", Beruni described 1,116 different medicines. Of these, 750 are obtained from various plants, 101 from 11 animals, and 107 from minerals. Beruni's works "Monuments of Ancient Generations" and "India" also contain interesting information about the structure of plants and animals and their interaction with the external environment. Based on his natural scientific observations and experiments, Beruni concludes that natural phenomena are governed by certain natural laws, and that no external force can change them.

Abu Ali ibn Sina (980–1037 AD) is known as a great encyclopedist. He wrote 450 works, 240 of which have survived to our time. Among Ibn Sina's works, the masterpiece "The Canons of Medicine" is an encyclopedia of medical science and is considered the pinnacle of the spread of medieval medical science. Ibn Sina's philosophical and medical scientific views are set out in his world-famous work "Kitab al-Shifa", that is, "The Book of Healing". This work describes philosophical concepts such as matter, space, time, form, motion, existence, as well as ideas about sciences such as mathematics, chemistry, botany, ecology, geology, astronomy, and psychology. Ibn Sina's ideas about various natural processes such as the formation of mountains, the change of the earth's surface over time, and the occurrence of earthquakes made a great contribution to the development of geological science.

Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur (1483–1530). Babur was not only a poet, but also a king, hunter, historian, gardener and naturalist. In the work "Baburnoma", Babur described the nature, wealth, customs, fauna and flora of the places he visited. The work contains many folk sayings related to land, water and air. In his work, Babur described the geographical location of the place, the climate it belongs to, its flora and fauna, and noted that since ancient times in Central Asia there have been several varieties of melons, wheat, apricots, pears and fruits. In the work, Babur

compared the nature and specific features of the places he visited with Andijan and gave a detailed description of the fauna of Central Asia, Afghanistan, Khorasan and India.

Introducing children to nature in preschool educational institutions is of great importance in raising them to be spiritually mature, moral, and pure people. The purpose of the article is to prepare preschool children for school, to introduce them to nature, to be careful about nature, to be kind to the Motherland, to implement ecological education, and to educate young people with excellent knowledge of nature.

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